

NEWSLETTER 03

February 28th, 2024

SMA TB

Letter from the SMA-TB coordinator

“ As we navigate a world recovering from the challenges posed by the remnants of the COVID-19 pandemic, our study teams have united to triumph over the obstacles brought about by lockdowns and personal losses. Despite the difficulties of the past years, our collective resilience and commitment shine through. It is heartening to witness how, in the face of adversity, our consortium members have not only overcome hurdles but also strengthened our resolve to move forward. The positive spirit and collaborative efforts demonstrated by everyone involved are a testament to our shared dedication and determination to make meaningful progress in our project. Together, we embrace the opportunities ahead with optimism and enthusiasm.

As mentioned on previous occasions, SMA-TB Clinical Trial (CT), originally scheduled to conclude by June 2024, has been influenced significantly by the COVID-19 pandemic, as highlighted in scientific literature and acknowledged by the WHO. The impact of the pandemic on tuberculosis (TB) diagnosis has consequently affected the recruitment rate and posed challenges to the trial's timeline. Budget constraints are also placing additional pressure on the recruitment period and the overall progress of the SMA-TB project.

The CT team, in collaboration with the Trial Steering Committee (TSC) (Prof. Anne Ma Dyrhol-Riise, Prof. Helen McShane and Prof. Willem Hanekom) and the Data Safety Management Board (DSMB) (Prof. Salome Charalambous, Prof. Petros Karakousis and Dr. Sebastià Videla), has been actively working to maximize the number of individuals recruited in the trial. Our focus is on ensuring participant safety, addressing scientific inquiries, and optimizing the utilization of available public resources. This has motivated the development of a new statistical analysis plan by Dr. Kennedy Otwombe (WITS Health Consortium - Perinatal HIV Research Unit, WHC-PHRU) the statistician of the CT, with the advisory of an external expert (Dr. Andrew Copas, University College London, Infection & Population Health).

We are proud to announce that, in spite of all the challenges and constraints, by 22 January 2024, 223 patients have been enrolled, reaching 63% and surpassing the milestone required by the European Commission (EC) of more than 50% of patients recruited.

Once again, I extend my heartfelt gratitude to each consortium partner for their unwavering dedication and collaborative spirit. Together, we have made remarkable strides towards achieving our main goals. Additionally, I express deep appreciation to the members of our boards for their invaluable advice, which has played a pivotal role in guiding our efforts. The success of our project is a testament to the collective commitment and synergy within our consortium. As we move forward, I am confident that our continued collaboration will lead to even greater accomplishments and thank you all for your exceptional contributions and ongoing support. ”

Dr. Cris Vilaplana
SMA-TB Coordinator

Partner Perspectives: Insights from Dr. Ziyaad Waja, WHC-PHRU

“ Together, we have strengthened our resolve to make SMA-TB a success. Despite the disappointment experienced over the past 2 years with low recruitment numbers and a general lack of TB testing, we have overcome and implemented strategies that will not only move us forward on the SMA-TB project but has enhanced us as public health practitioners looking to improve life through research.

Our stakeholder engagements are more productive and our unit functions seamlessly with the national health department to broaden our reach within communities and fight the TB crisis in Sub-Saharan Africa.

We have mobilised personnel to track TB cases at home, set up community engagement campaigns and collaborated with local clinics to ensure that TB testing is not being ignored. Participant education has also been key to our success in treating patients and ensuring better adherence to treatment and follow-up visits resulting in earlier detection of adverse events and better vigilance of trial participants in general.

The SMA-TB project has provided our staff with unique learning experiences, from the design of the trial to the revolutionary types of biomarker specimens collected enhancing our skills as a unit. We have also increased our own lab capacity which a year ago seemed quite impossible. We take this opportunity to thank all consortium partners for their amazing support and unique skills that make this collaboration a success. ”

Dr. Ziyaad Waja

SMA-TB WHC-PHRU Team

SMA-TB Scientific Progress

SMA-TB submitted all the deliverables regarding the work related to this objective and successfully achieved all the milestones except the last patient first visit, as the CT is still active.

By 22 January 2024, **223 patients** have been **enrolled**, reaching the 63% and surpassing the milestone required by the EC of more than 50% patients recruited.

Consortium partners involved in work package (WP) 2 have worked with samples from previously established cohorts and first batches of SMA-TB samples (up to **15,179 samples**). WP3 has identified **potential biomarkers** using a systems biology approach involving mathematical modeling. Additionally, we have initiated the **setup of the model** using the dataset provided by partners in WP2, laying the groundwork for the forthcoming analysis with SMA-TB generated data. Notably, certain proteins have been singled out as promising biomarkers, warranting further investigation.

SMA-TB Leaflet about TB

The SMA-TB project, in partnership with the Public Health Agency of Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain (ASPB), has created a leaflet designed to offer straightforward and essential information to local vulnerable communities. The content, a collaborative effort between Institut de Recerca Germans Trias i Pujol (IGTP), ASPB, and the Germans Trias i Pujol Hospital (HUGTiP), was complemented by visually appealing graphics crafted by professional designers, Laura Ginès and Pepón Meneses. To ensure widespread accessibility, the leaflet has been produced in 12 languages - English, Afrikaans, Georgian, Ukrainian, Polish, Spanish, Catalan, Portuguese, French, Italian, German, and Norwegian - thanks to the collaborative efforts of all SMA-TB partners. The [leaflet](#) was uploaded in Zenodo in order others can reuse it.

SMA-TB Project Results

[Public deliverables and other reports](#) are available.

SMA-TB has been using the EU OpenAIRE Repository Zenodo and created the [SMA-TB Zenodo](#) community to openly publish templates generated as part of the SMA-TB Capacity-building toolkit, which others can freely download, adapt and reuse.

A capacity-building toolkit which includes protocols, videos and others was developed within the 1st period and updated during the 2nd one. This [toolkit](#) is available for public download.

It was released on 23 December 2022, and has already garnered **541 downloads**. The leaflet was utilized in a TB screening intervention for Ukrainian war refugees in Barcelona, orchestrated by the ASPB in collaboration with the SMA-TB project.

SMA-TB Annual Meeting in Toulouse

The second SMA-TB annual meeting was held from 11 to 13 May 2022 in Toulouse, France, organized by partner Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique - Institute of Pharmacology and Structural Biology (CNRS-IPBS), and members of SMA-TB External Scientific Advisory Board (ESAB) were invited and attended the meeting. The consortium began with a presentation about the **progress and challenges of the RCT** (WP1) that is performed by the sites WHC-PHRU (South Africa) and National Center of Tuberculosis and Lung Diseases (NCTLD, Georgia) and the trial's sponsor (IGTP). A big challenge for the project is the low recruitment rate which had an impact on the other WPs.

Partners engaged in WP2, aimed at identifying pathogen and host factors predictive of disease progression and intervention response, have affirmed that **SMA-TB will yield a sufficient number of samples for processing and drawing anticipated conclusions**. The partners have diligently established techniques and processed samples from ongoing cohorts, aligning with the details outlined in the project's Grant Agreement (GA). In WP3, an *in silico* model is being developed using SMA-TB Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) data, which is subsequently refined with data from other clinical trials conducted by partners with a similar focus as the SMA-TB trial.

The partners presented their carefully devised **strategy for future activities**, drawing on evidence published in the existing literature. Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities performed during the 2nd year of the project were presented by WP4 tasks' leaders. Finally, IGTP presented the actual status of Deliverables and Milestones planned for this period. All of them were submitted and achieved within the timeframe described in the GA.

SMA-TB Annual Meeting in Tbilisi

The third SMA-TB annual meeting was held from 27 to 29 June 2023 in Tbilisi, Georgia, organized by partner – NCTLD. Two Georgian Government representatives (Mrs. Tamar Gabunia, Deputy minister of Health; and Mr. Nodar Papukishvili, Deputy minister of Education and Science), as well as Prof. Zaza Avaliani, director of the NCTLD were present and introduced the event.

There were several members from the different boards (TSC, DSMB, ESAB and the Ethics Advisory Board, EAB) attending, face to face or online, as well as the representative of Horizon EC office in Georgia, representatives of European Lung Foundation and the coordinator of DRTB-HDT project.

The **results achieved so far were presented** by each SMA-TB WP team. The main achievement is having reached the recruitment of 61% of the initially estimated sample size (WP1). Several biomarkers were identified as potentially useful to assess severity and to monitor treatment (WP2), and therefore with the potential to be included in the stratification algorithm to be developed (WP3).

WP4 and WP5 have also presented their activities and reports. The SMA-TB ESAB's members provided feedback on the work conducted and at the end of the meeting made considerations on the overall progress of the tasks planned. All of them congratulated the consortium, and advised on how to proceed during this remaining time of the project.

The meeting included a scheduled **visit to the NCTLD**, providing attendees with the opportunity to explore the site's facilities and meet the dedicated staff involved in the SMA-TB project. Prof. Zaza Avaliani, the director of NCTLD, shared insights into the hospital's history and its deep connections with Georgian society. NCTLD has long been acknowledged as a Center of Excellence for specialized TB services. Annually, NCTLD caters to approximately one-third of all registered TB patients in the country, offering both inpatient and outpatient care. This translates to around **8,000 outpatient visits, 1,500 hospitalizations for elderly patients, and 200 hospitalizations for pediatric patients each year.**

The visit provided valuable insights into the clinical research conducted at NCTLD, the TB detection program targeting vulnerable groups, and its pivotal role in TB diagnosis and treatment throughout the Caucasus region. NCTLD's contributions extend to regional capacity building, showcasing its leadership in the field.

Thank you NCTLD SMA-TB Team!

SMA-TB WP2 Meeting in Paris

Several members of the SMA-TB Consortium actively participated in the Union World Conference on Lung Health 2023, hosted in Paris, France, from 15 to 18 November. Among the highlights of the conference was **Nino Gogichadze (IGTP) having the honor of presenting her PhD thesis work** within the SMA-TB project's WP2 as an oral abstract.

Noteworthy attendees included Dr. Neil Martinson (WHC-PHRU) and Dr. Nestan Tukvadze (NCTLD), who represented WP1. Dr. Jérôme Nigou (CNRS-IPBS), acting as the leader of WP2, and Dr. Cris Vilaplana (IGTP), serving as the project coordinator, convened over dinner to engage in a **comprehensive discussion about the progress of the clinical trial**. Key topics addressed during the meeting encompassed concerns related to timeline constraints, the seamless integration of WP1 outputs with WP2 tasks, and immediate next steps.

The conversation also delved into exploring **additional funding possibilities** beyond the current scope of the SMA-TB project. This collaborative dialogue reflects the dedication of the consortium towards advancing research and addressing challenges in the field of TB.

SMA-TB Communication & Dissemination

As of now, the SMA-TB consortium has successfully published **7 Open Access Publications** and presented **12 posters and talks**. Additionally, SMA-TB partners are actively engaging with mass media to ensure that knowledge about the project reaches all stakeholders and the general public.

In this regard, Dr. Jérôme Nigou (CNRS-IPBS) has contributed significantly by providing two insightful interviews on [RadioFrance](#) and [RTS](#). These interviews are focused on the latest techniques in diagnosing TB, further contributing to the project's visibility and impact.

SMA-TB & Local Communities

SMA-TB is actively undertaking various initiatives to **engage local communities and stakeholders** in Georgia, South Africa (CT sites), and Spain. In Georgia and South Africa, multiple meetings with Community Advisory Board (CAB) members have been conducted. These sessions serve the dual purpose of disseminating information about the study's ongoing developments and seeking valuable feedback from CAB members regarding the project.

In Spain, the IGTP team, working collaboratively with clinicians from HUGTiP, has actively sought to **identify TB patients and arrange meetings with them**. This approach not only strengthens patient engagement but also fosters a mutually beneficial exchange of benefits. Furthermore, the coordinator has established connections with cultural and social organizations, the Public Health System of Barcelona, and the [UITB Foundation](#). The aim is to raise awareness about the SMA-TB project and organize collaborative public activities.

These activities, such as the SMA-TB TB leaflet (see above) are designed to communicate the project's objectives to civil society, particularly individuals from vulnerable populations, while actively seeking feedback.

SMA-TB Training activities

IGTP, the SMA-TB project coordinator, hosted Natasha Pillay from the WHC-PHRU to provide training on SMA-TB sample processing. Additionally, they collaborated on some aspects of WP2, specifically on Task 2.1 related to Host-Directed Therapy in a RCT. This collaboration included engagement with various public agencies.

Joint activities & other projects

As much as possible, SMA-TB is linking up with other projects funded by the EC within the different programmes.

With the [DRTB-HDT](#) project (GA N° 847465), which was funded in the same H2020 call as SMA-TB, Prof. Salome Charalambous from the Aurum Institute (institutional coordinator of the DRTB-HDT project) was included as a member of the SMA-TB EAB and the DSMB of the SMA-TB CT. She has attended all our annual meetings, and has been very active in helping us in the implementation of risk management measures to overcome the problem of the slow recruitment due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

With [INNOVA4TB](#), a MSCA H2020 project, SMA-TB was invited to participate in the INNOVA4TB Annual Meeting by the end of 2022, and also in the INNOVA4TB training day and meeting. The INNOVA4TB members participated in the TB screening event carried out by the ASBP and the SMA-TB project.

With [ADVANCE-TB](#), a COST Action (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, CA21164), SMA-TB is organizing a joint workshop in 22 and 23 May 2024 focused on defeating tuberculosis. It will have the participation of international experts who will discuss about challenges, breakthroughs and lessons learnt from projects including clinical trials.

Next events

3 & 4 June 2024

The **WP2 meeting** will take place in Oslo hosted by the [Oslo universitetssykehus](#) (Oslo University Hospital).

2 - 4 December 2024

The **final meeting** of the SMA-TB project will be held in Barcelona from 2 to 4 December this year hosted by IGTP. It will be a two-day closed meeting for the consortium's partners and an open session to the public and stakeholders.

SMA TB

If you are interested in knowing more about the SMA-TB project or want to collaborate, please do not hesitate to contact us:

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